

Late Jōmon Ainu “three” **re* and Proto-Sino-Tibetan “three” **dVm* (**dām*)

Alexander Akulov

independent scholar; Saint Petersburg, Russia; e-mail: aynu@inbox.ru

Abstract

Previously, it was noted that Late Jōmon Ainu (LJA) “three” **re* could not be compared with Proto-Sino-Tibetan (PST)/Proto-Tibeto-Burman (PTB) “three” **g-sum*. Instead, LJA **re* was compared with Tangut “three” **rejr* and modern Dumi “three” *ryekbo*. Reconstructing “three” for PTB/PST as **g-sum* is completely incorrect because this form is identical to the form *g-sum* existing in modern Tibetan. Taking modern Tibetan forms in their unaltered form and postulating them as the PTB/PST forms is anything but science. Furthermore, within the Sino-Tibetan languages, there are forms for “three” derived from the stem *rV[C]*, which cannot be derived from **g-sum*. A more accurate reconstruction for PST/PTB “three” would fuse stems *sVm* and *rVm*, creating a proto-form from which both can be derived. This form is **dVm* (**dām*). And **dām* correlates perfectly with LJA **re*.

Keywords: Ainu language; Sino-Tibetan family; Proto-Tibeto-Burman language; comparative linguistics; Ainu-Minoan stock

1. Introduction to the problem

In a paper devoted to comparing of Ainu numerals “one”, “two”, “three”, “four”, “five” with their Sino-Tibetan counterparts it was said that Late Jōmon Ainu (LJA) “three” **re* can’t be compared with the Proto-Tibeto-Burman numeral “three” **g-sum*, and LJA **re* was compared with Tangut “three” *rejr* and with modern Dumi¹ “three” *ryekbo* (Akulov, Nonno 2025: 5).

Of course it is more correct to compare proto-forms than a proto-form with a modern form. However, between the time of existence of LJA and the time of existence of Proto-Tibeto-Burman (PTB) / Proto-Sino-Tibetan (PST) there is a serious time gap.

The modern Ainu dialects began to diverge approximately during the Late Jōmon period (1500 – 300 BCE), or even earlier (Nonno 2015: 64). Therefore, by using materials represented in modern Ainu dialects it is possible to restore LJA that existed in about 1500 – 300 BCE. It is currently believed that PST existed in southwest China in the middle of the 12th millennium BCE (van Driem 2005). However, taking into account the fact that Jōmon pottery was created by the immediate ancestors of the historical Ainu (Akulov 2015), and that the earliest layers of Jōmon date back to the beginning of the 14th millennium BCE (Pearson 2006), it becomes clear that the time of the existence of PST should be shifted back by at least three millennia, since Proto-Ainu started to separate from PST with the beginning of Jōmon period.

Thus, between LJA and PST there is a time gap of about 10 – 12 thousand years, and in this case it generally doesn't matter whether we compare LJA forms with PST forms or modern Ainu forms with PST forms.

However, the fact that earlier about 30 LJA lexical items were successfully compared with PST/PTB counterparts (Akulov, Nonno 2024) suggests that in this case comparing can be made

¹ Dumi is one of Tibeto-Burman language of the Kiranti branch.

without any confusion about the large time distance between the two languages. This case shows that glottochronological methods do not always work; the Ainu language is a language that challenges glottochronology.

In fact, reconstructing the **g-sum* form for the numeral "three" in Proto-Tibeto-Burman is categorically incorrect. Proto-Tibeto-Burman (PTB) / Proto-Sino-Tibetan (PST) had a completely different form, which can be very well compared to the LJA form **re*. In this short paper I want to show why the reconstruction of the form **g-sum* for "three" for PTB/PST is incorrect and to represent a more accurate reconstruction, which also correlates well with the LJA form for "three" **re*.

2. Why it is incorrect to reconstruct the form **g-sum* for "three" for PTB/PST?

To reconstruct "three" for PYB/PST as **g-sum* is categorically incorrect.

Firstly, because the form **g-sum* is exactly the form that exists in the historical/modern Tibetan language – *g-sum*. Taking modern Tibetan forms in their unaltered form and postulating that these were the PTB forms is anything but science.

Secondly, because in the Sino-Tibetan languages there are forms of the numeral three derived from the stem *rV[C]*. For example, in the Tangut language, there were two forms for the numeral "three": *rejr (lhejr)*², and *so*³. And if the form *so* can easily be traced back to the proto-form **g-sum*, then the form *rejr (lhejr)* is absolutely impossible.

In this case, supporters of the Tibetan-centric reconstruction of Proto-Tibeto-Burman usually object that the Tangut form *rejr (lhejr)* belonged to a special ritual register of the language, that it is unique and allegedly has no analogues in other Sino-Tibetan languages, that this form *rejr (lhejr)* is allegedly a borrowing from an unknown pre-Sino-Tibetan substrate.

However, similar forms for the numeral "three" for some reason exist in a number of Tibeto-Burman languages. For example, as it has been already mentioned above, in Dumi "three" is *ryekbo* (Akulov, Nonno 2025: 5). Also in the Konyakian languages⁴, in particular, for example, in Nocte Naga "three" is *dak ram*, where *dak* is a special word used to form numerals, and the numeral "three" itself is *ram*⁵; in Hakhun Tangsa "three" is *m̂-r̂m* (the stem meaning "three" is *r̂m*); in the Konyak language itself, "three" is *l̂m / lim*, and in the Wancho language "three" is *aram / aram* – here we can see the same stem *ram / ram*.

Thus, it is quite obvious that the Tangut form *rejr (lhejr)* is not at all unique, does not exist in vacuum, but has quite visible correspondences in other Tibeto-Burman languages. And also the fact that supporters of the Tibetan-centric reconstruction simply throw out the Tangut form *rejr (lhejr)*, pointing to its supposed uniqueness, does not lend itself to a normal, sane explanation within the framework of ordinary scientific logic. Such selective use of linguistic material for reconstruction has nothing in common with normal comparative-historical linguistics.

² Li 1997.

³ Wiktionary 2026.

⁴ Konyakian (Northern Naga) languages belong to the Sal branch of the Tibeto-Burman languages. These languages are spoken by the Naga hill peoples of northeastern India and northwestern Myanmar.

⁵ The data for the Konyakian languages presented in this article were obtained using artificial intelligence systems.

It should also be noted that in ritual languages (ritual registers of language) it is usually the archaic vocabulary that is preserved, and therefore, when faced with such a form as the Tangust form *rejr* (*lhejr*), researchers should not throw it, but on the contrary, take it as the basis for reconstruction, because, most likely, it is closer to the proto-language state than other forms.

3. The true reconstruction of the PST form “three”

It is noteworthy that at present, the form **s-rum* with the meaning “three” is reconstructed for Old Chinese (Baxter, Sagart 2014: 75), and the stem of this form is *rum*.

It is possible that for Proto-Sino-Tibetan can be reconstructed two forms for the numeral “three”, but perhaps it would be more correct to reconstruct a form close to **s-rum*, that is, combining both the form *rum* and the form *sum*.

In particular, it is noteworthy that a very interesting form for the numeral “three” exists in the Tutsa language⁶ – *ezom* – clearly a transitional form from *ram* to *sam*.

There are two options here.

The first is to reconstruct a form for the numeral “three” similar to the ancient Chinese form, that is, **srVm* – this would be a form that simply mechanically combines two stems existing in modern/historical Sino-Tibetan languages.

The second option is to reconstruct a form in which both stems (*sVm* and *rVm*) are fused together, creating a proto-form from which both *sVm* and *rVm* can be derived. This variant is **dVm*.

It is quite easy to transform the form **dVm* to both *rVm*, and to *sVm* via *zVm* (see Fig. 1).

The second option is much more preferable, given that in the Yeniseian languages, which are related to the Sino-Tibetan languages (Akulov 2019), the proto-form for the numeral “three” is **doʔŋa*⁷. The Yeniseian languages separated from the Sino-Tibetan ‘trunk’ much earlier than the Ainu language (Akulov 2025: 36 – 38), and therefore it is completely logical that the Proto-Yeniseian form for “three” correlates well with the corresponding Proto-Sino-Tibetan form. (Now it is possible to state that Proto-Ainu started to separate from the Proto-Sino-Tibetan in about 14th – 12th millennia BCE, with the beginning of the Jōmon culture, while the ancestor of the Proto-Yeniseian language separated from the Sino-Tibetan ‘trunk’ in about before 22nd millennium BCE.)

Thus, for the Proto-Sino-Tibetan state, the form **dVm* should be reconstructed for the numeral “three.” It should be noted that the form *rVm* is an earlier form, closer to the proto-form **dVm* than the form *zVm*, because the sounds [d] and [r] are very close, very similar in articulation: the sound [r] is often pronounced and heard as [d], and the distance between [d] and [z] is more significant.

⁶ Tutsa language also is one of the Konyakian languages, it is spread in the northeastern part of India.

⁷ Starostin 2005

Furthermore, I would like to emphasize that it is categorically incorrect to use the modern/historical Tibetan language as the main base for Proto-Sino-Tibetan reconstructions. This practice is clearly based not on linguistic but on political grounds. It is linked to the general enthusiastic attitude toward Tibet that is quite widespread among orientalists.

Fig. 1. Scheme showing the history of the forms of the numeral "three" in the Sino-Tibetan languages

In fact, the languages of the Bodish branch/group are by no means the most archaic of the Tibeto-Burman languages; they are simply one of many. And if we talk about the most archaic Sino-Tibetan languages, then one of the most archaic groups/branches is definitely the Qiang group.

All existing Sino-Tibetan reconstructions actually need to be re-examined and possibly corrected. And, in general, it should be understood that existing reconstructions are not the ultimate truth, but merely a set of probabilities, a set of versions of how things could have been. A probability value should be shown next to each reconstruction.

4. The index of similarity of LJA **re* and PST **dVm*

To make conclusion about resemblance of two forms be less speculative, it is useful to calculate the degree of similarity of LJA **re* and PST **dVm*.

The algorithm of calculation the degree of similarity is described in Akulov, Nonno 2025: 7 – 9.

It seems that in the form **dVm*, instead of the indefinite vowel [V], it is most logical to reconstruct [ə] – the so-called neutral vowel.

[re] ~ [dəm]:

[r] ~ [d] = (voiced alveolar flap consonant) ~ (voiced alveolar plosive consonant) = $(\frac{3}{4} + \frac{3}{4})/2 = 0.75$;

[e] ~ [e] = (high-mid front unrounded vowel) ~ (mid central vowel) = $(\frac{2}{5} + \frac{2}{3})/2 \approx 0.53$;

[m] has no correspondences in [re], so in this case the degree of similarity is zero.

And thus, [re] ~ [dəm] = $(0.75 + 0/53 + 0)/3 \approx 0.42$.

This degree of similarity is higher than the degree of similarity between Russian form *pyat'* [p'ætʲ] "five" and English *five*, which is 0.33 (Akulov, Nonno 2025: 9), but lower than the degree of similarity between Russian *tri* [tri] "three" and English *three* which is 0.52 (Akulov, Nonno 2025: 8 – 9).

References

- Alexander Akulov. 2015. The closure of *corpok-kur* problem or once again on relationship between Jōmon and Ainu. *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 1, № 2; pp.: 17 – 31
- Akulov A. 2025. The Nivkh language is a 'bridge' between the Sino-Tibetan and the Yeniseian languages. *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 11, N 1: pp.: 24 – 44
- Akulov A. 2019. Yeniseian languages and Ainu-Minoan stock. *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 5, № 3; pp: 12 – 17
- Akulov A., Nonno T. 2025. Comparing Ainu numerals "one", "two", "three", "four", "five" with their Sino-Tibetan counterparts. *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 11, N 2; pp.: 1 – 20
- Akulov A., Nonno T. 2024. Some lexical correspondences between the Ainu language and the Sino-Tibetan family. *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 10, N 1; pp.: 16 – 39
- Baxter W. H., Sagart L. 2014. *Old Chinese: A New Reconstruction*, New York: Oxford University Press
- Li Fanwen 李范文 1997. *Xià-Hàn Zìdiǎn* 夏漢字典 Tangut – Chinese Dictionary. Social Sciences Press (中国社会科学出版社). Beijing
- Nonno T. 2015. Some preliminary thoughts on the structure of Late Jōmon Ainu language. *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 1, № 2; pp.: 64 – 67
- Pearson R. 2006. Jomon Hot Spot: Increasing Sedentism in South-Western Japan in the Incipient Jomon (14,000-9250 cal. BC) and Earliest Jomon (9250-5300 cal. BC) Periods. *World Archaeology. Sedentism in Non-Agricultural Societies*. 38 (2); pp.: 240 – 242
- Starostin S. A. 2005. Yeniseian etymology database *doʔŋa "three"

https://starlingdb.org/cgi-bin/response.cgi?single=1&basename=%2fDATA%2fYENISEY%2fYENET&text_number=297&rot=config – accessed February 2026

van Driem G. 2005. Tibeto-Burman vs Indo-Chinese, in Sagart, Laurent; Blench, Roger; Sanchez-Mazas, Alicia (eds.), *The Peopling of East Asia: Putting Together Archaeology, Linguistics and Genetics*, London: Routledge Curzon, pp. 81–106

Wiktionary 2026. Sino-Tibetan Swadesh lists. Appendix
[https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/Appendix:Sino-Tibetan Swadesh lists](https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/Appendix:Sino-Tibetan_Swadesh_lists) – accessed February 2026